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Examination Anxiety As Correlate Of Students Academic Achievement In Public Secondary Schools In Anambra State

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ABSTRACT

The study determined the correlation between examination anxiety and students' academic achievement in public secondary schools in Anambra state. Two research questions guided the study and two hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance. The correlational research design was adopted for the study. The population of the study comprised 21,272 senior secondary school students in SS2 in 267 public secondary schools in Anambra State. The population comprised of 9550 male students and 11,722 female students in 267 public secondary schools in Anambra State. Questionnaire on Examination Anxiety of Public Secondary School Students (QEAPSSS) and Students' Academic Achievement Scores (SAAS) were used to collect data for the study. The QEAPSSS was subjected to face and construct validation. The application of Cronbach Alpha reliability method yielded coefficient values of 0.87 and 0.84 for cluster 1 and 2 respectively with an overall reliability coefficient of 0.86. Pearson Product Moment Correlation statistics was used to answer the research questions and test the hypotheses. Finding of the study revealed that a high negative relationship exists between somatic examination anxiety and academic achievement of public secondary school students in Anambra State. Findings further showed that a very high negative relationship exists between somatic examination anxiety and academic achievement of public secondary school students in Anambra State. The findings also showed that somatic and cognitive examination anxiety significantly predicts students' academic achievement in public secondary schools in Anambra state. The researcher recommended among others that principals of public secondary schools should implement regular relaxation and mindfulness training sessions for students so as to reduce the level of somatic examination anxiety.

Keywords: Examination Anxiety, Somatic, Cognitive, Academic Achievement, Students

INTRODUCTION

Secondary school education is the stage of learning that students undergo after primary school and before entering tertiary education. Its significance lies in its role as a bridge between primary and tertiary education, and in preparing individuals for productive lives within society. According to the Federal Republic of Nigeria (FRN, 2013), the broad goals of secondary education in Nigeria are to prepare individuals for meaningful living within society and for higher education. The FRN in Iwuanyanwu and Uwadiogwu (2019) stated that the objectives of secondary education include providing trained manpower in applied science, technology, and commerce at sub-professional levels; inspiring students with a desire for self-improvement and excellence; fostering a generation of individuals, who can think independently, respect the views and feelings of others, and uphold the dignity of labour. The realization of the goals of public secondary education is reflected in the academic achievement of students.

Academic achievement pertains to an individual's achievement in specific academic areas, such as mathematics, English, or science. It signifies the learning outcomes of students who engage in education and practice and is evaluated by their cumulative grade point average which represents the average of their grades or marks. Through problem-solving in exams using questions and answer options, students engage in cognitive and mental processes of learning. In a recent study, academic achievement was linked to the percentage of marks obtained by students in their most recent examinations (Nwanze et al., 2021). Academic achievement is crucial for students as it influences their ability to accomplish their goals. Onwugbufor and Udebuana (2021) defined academic achievement as the knowledge or skills acquired in school subjects, evaluated by test results or grades awarded by instructors. Horsfall and Wordu (2023) stated that academic achievement represents the outcome of a student's learning efforts within the school context, encompassing the overall academic achievement evaluated through teacher assessments and examinations. To determine academic achievement, students must be regularly assessed and evaluated through tests and examinations to determine their knowledge and competence in various subjects. Although, Horsfall and Wordu (2023) noted that examinations are not the sole means of assessing and evaluating knowledge, they have become the primary and most practical method of assessment in schools. Consequently, examinations are a period of intense activity in secondary schools throughout Nigeria, including Anambra State.

Every year, students in secondary schools in Anambra State participate in examinations at least three times during a school session. These examination periods are considered the highlight of each term, marking a time when students become more focused on their academic work. However, during these times, some students tend to fall ill or feel depressed. Examinations are perceived as critical periods in the school calendar, and the significant pressure leads to high levels of stress, nervousness, and apprehension among students (Agnes et al., 2022). This pressure results in some students ultimately missing their exams. This issue seems prevalent in secondary schools across Nigeria and particularly in Anambra State, where students are more likely to visit health centres during examination periods (Ilo & Unchukwu, 2020). According to Horsfall and Wordu (2023), this is due to the anxiety experienced by students.

Examination anxiety is defined as an irrational fear that leads to avoidance of the feared situation or object, thereby intensifying the anxiety. It involves excessive worry about upcoming examinations, lifestyle issues, negative thinking, and apprehension about the consequences of failure. Examination anxiety refers to the anxiety associated with taking tests and exams, including the fear of failing and the negative outcomes associated with it, such as psychological hyperarousal, negative thought patterns, a desire to escape from or avoid evaluative situations, poor test achievement, and difficulty focusing on the task at hand, regardless of whether these fears are realistic. Horsfall and Wordu (2023) defined examination anxiety as a psychological condition where individuals experience extreme stress, phobia, discomfort, and irrational fear during or before examinations. Examination anxiety has become a common aspect of the academic world. It manifests as self-preoccupation, leading to self-minimization, which results in harmful mental evaluation. This can cause concentration issues, adverse physiological reactions, and academic failure. Hamzah et al. (2018) also describe examination anxiety as occurring specifically in examination situations. It can have either positive or negative effects on students. In this study, examination anxiety refers to any emotional or psychological factor that can either hinder or enhance an individual's achievement in an examination or testing situation. Patil and Aithala (2017) described examination anxiety as situational anxiety triggered by exam situations. It occurs when a student has a predisposition to exhibit a certain level of anxiety, whether high or low, across different subjects, regardless of the content or difficulty of the exam. Examination anxiety can have both adaptive and maladaptive effects, primarily depending on the intensity of the anxiety experienced by the student (Horsfall & Wordu, 2023).

Examination anxiety is an undesirable reaction to evaluation and is the most significant problem faced by students in their education (Dinga et al., 2018). Examination anxiety is a psychological condition where students experience extreme distress and anxiety in test situations. While a small amount of anxiety during exams can be beneficial by motivating students and aiding learning, excessive anxiety negatively impacts academic achievement (Oluoch et al., 2018). The psychological symptoms that build up in students before a test include restlessness, unusual body movements, difficulty

concentrating, insomnia, fatigue, muscle contractions, abdominal pain, and tremors (Ilo & Unchukwu, 2020). Alemu and Feyssa (2020) distinguished between generalized anxiety disorders and examination anxiety, noting that generalized anxiety is characterized by trait anxiety, causing students to experience high levels of stress in various situations. In contrast, examination anxiety is a state of anxiety leading to heightened nervousness specifically related to exams. Symptoms of examination anxiety can range from moderate to severe. Various factors contributing to examination anxiety among students include individual, school, and parental factors (Patil & Aithala, 2017). Examination anxiety has the potential to cause a child to express self-doubt during a test. Bekomson and Mgbani (2019) found that most students experience self-doubt and lack the ability to manage difficult academic tasks. Amalu (2020) argued that there is a relationship between the extent to which learners experience examination anxiety and the scores they receive on a specific test, while others believe that the relationship between examination anxiety and learners' achievement is relatively insignificant. Okobia and Oji (2021) averred that there are basically two types of examination anxiety; one type of examination anxiety is somatic (affective) and the second type is cognitive.

Somatic examination anxiety refers to the physical symptoms and bodily manifestations of anxiety experienced by students during academic evaluations or assessments, such as tests or exams. These physical symptoms can potentially impact a student's academic achievement. Somatic examination anxiety involves a range of physiological reactions associated with the autonomic nervous system's response to stress. These reactions may include increased heart rate, sweating, muscle tension, nausea, dry mouth, and trembling (Zeidner in Robert, 2017). These physical symptoms can be distressing and distracting for students, potentially interfering with their ability to concentrate and perform optimally during exams or assessments. Researcher have found a negative relationship between somatic examination anxiety and academic achievement. For instance, Cassady and Johnson in Popovska et al (2024) reported that higher levels of somatic anxiety were associated with lower academic achievement among undergraduate students. Similarly, Popovska et al (2024) found that somatic anxiety was a significant predictor of lower test achievement in college students, even after controlling for other factors such as study habits and cognitive test anxiety. The physical manifestations of somatic examination anxiety can have a detrimental effect on cognitive processing and working memory, which are essential for successful achievement on academic tasks (Wadi et al., 2022). The physiological arousal and bodily sensations associated with somatic anxiety can divert attention away from the task at hand, making it more difficult for students to focus, retrieve information from memory, and effectively apply their knowledge. Additionally, somatic examination anxiety can lead to avoidance behaviors, such as procrastination or incomplete preparation, which can further undermine academic achievement (Ilo & Unchukwu, 2020). Students experiencing somatic anxiety may also be more likely to engage in negative self-talk or rumination, exacerbating their anxiety and further impairing their achievement (Wadi et al., 2022). Similarly, cognitive examination anxiety is another form of examination anxiety.

Cognitive examination anxiety involves negative thoughts, worries, and rumination related to evaluation situations, such as exams or assessments. Students experiencing cognitive anxiety may have difficulty concentrating, retrieving information from memory, and organizing their thoughts during exams or assessments (Ilo & Unchukwu, 2020). The cognitive component of examination anxiety, often referred to as worry anxiety, is primarily cognitive in nature but is accompanied by emotional aspects. This component is represented by what is known as the worry dimension. Worry dimension is defined as any mental expression of a person's concern about the quality of their own achievement (Popovska et al., 2024). Consequently, an anxious person, instead of focusing all their cognitive abilities on solving the task, spends a lot of time thinking about the implications and consequences of their own failure, which they believe is inevitable. Since the activation of examination anxiety involves the initiation of a specific subtype of stress process, it is crucial to recognise the thoughts that perpetuate this vicious cycle. Such subjective assessment often causes individuals who are anxious about the exam to lose interest in solving the tasks and feel a strong desire to completely withdraw from the exam (Amalu, 2017). The worry dimension itself has numerous negative consequences. Primarily, this way of thinking generates unpleasant emotional reactions that often last from the beginning of exam preparation, through the exam itself, and during the period of waiting for results.

Moreover, anxiety can intensify over time and become a chronic pattern in a person's cognitive functioning.

Studies have found a negative relationship between cognitive examination anxiety and academic achievement. Wadi et al. (2022) reported that cognitive anxiety was a significant predictor of lower academic achievement, even after controlling for other factors such as intelligence and prior achievement. Furthermore, cognitive examination anxiety can lead to avoidance behaviors, such as procrastination or incomplete preparation, which can further undermine academic achievement (Cassady & Johnson in Alemu & Feyssa, 2020). Students experiencing cognitive anxiety may also be more likely to engage in negative self-talk or rumination, exacerbating their anxiety and further impairing their achievement. The findings of Onukwufor and Ugwu (2017) revealed that examination anxiety significantly predicts students' achievement. However, this has not been empirically proven among students secondary schools in Anambra State. It is against this background that the researcher empirically determined the correlation between examination anxiety and students' academic achievement in public secondary schools in Anambra state.

Statement of the Problem

Examination is the hallmark of the academic life of every secondary school students. This is because success in examination is seen as the determination of how serious a student is about their academic life and expected success in life. This has made examination periods very tough period in the life of some students in secondary schools in Anambra State. Students tend to develop symptoms of examination anxiety during this period. Field observation by the researcher reveals that the numbers of students who fall sick during the period of examination in secondary schools in the State appear to be high. Many scholars have alluded that this fear and anxiety has made so many students resort to all forms of examination malpractices so as to get higher grades. The researcher wonders if this issue could have a relationship with students' academic achievement in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

Purpose of the Study

The main purpose of the study was to investigate the correlation between examination anxiety and academic achievement of public secondary school students in Anambra State. Specifically, the study sought to:

1. determine the relationship between somatic examination anxiety and academic achievement of public secondary school students in Anambra State.
2. ascertain the relationship between cognitive examination anxiety and academic achievement of public secondary school students in Anambra State.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study.

1. What is the relationship between somatic examination anxiety and academic achievement of public secondary school students in Anambra State?
2. What is the relationship between cognitive examination anxiety and academic achievement of public secondary school students in Anambra State?

Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance:

1. There is no significant relationship between somatic examination anxiety and academic achievement of public secondary students in Anambra State.
2. There is no significant relationship between cognitive examination anxiety and academic achievement of public secondary students in Anambra State.

RESEARCH METHOD

The study adopted the correlational research design. The study was carried out in Anambra state which is one of the thirty-six (36) states of the Federal Republic of Nigeria, located in the South-Eastern part of Nigeria. The population of the study comprised 21,272 senior secondary school students in SS2 in 267 public secondary schools in Anambra State. The population comprised of 9550 male students and 11,722 female students in 267 public secondary schools in Anambra State. The SS2 students were chosen for the study because they were not concerned about any external examination, and therefore

are more disposed to respond to the questionnaires attentively. The sample of the study was 400 (200 male and 200 female) secondary school students from the 267 public secondary schools in Anambra State. A multistage sampling technique was employed to determine the sample of the study. In the first stage, simple random sampling was used to select two education zones. In the second stage, stratified random sampling was used to pick five public secondary schools from each education zone, making a total of 10 schools. Using cluster sampling technique in the third stage, the first arm of SS2 students in the 10 selected schools were participants in the study. It was estimated that each arm of SS2 class had about 40 students, and the 10 classes yielded a total of 400 students.

Questionnaire on Examination Anxiety of Public Secondary School Students (QEAPSSS) was used to collect data for the study. The instrument has two main Sections – A and B. Section A contains one item on respondents’ background information covering gender while Section B contained a total of 25 items arranged in two Clusters, B1-B2. Cluster B1 contains 10 items on the somatic examination anxiety and Cluster B2 contained 15 items on cognitive examination anxiety. The questionnaire is structured on a 4- point rating scale of Strongly Agree (SA), Agree (A), Disagree (D) and Strongly Disagree (SD). Students’ Academic Achievement Scores (SAAS)’which is SS 2 students’ scores in English Language and Mathematics, collected from Recording Department, Post Primary School Service Commission (PPSSC), Awka Anambra State (2024).English Language and Mathematics were used for this study because they are general and compulsory subjects that determine the levels of students’ academic achievement.

The instrument was subjected to face and construct validation. For the face validation, the instruments were validated by three experts in the Faculty of Education, Nnamdi Azikiwe University, Awka. On the other hand, construct validated was carried out with the help of Principal Component Analysis approach with Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) as a measure of sampling adequacy to construct the Principal Component Analysis. The coefficient value of 0.80 was obtained. Furthermore, the instruments were subjected to a pilot test on 20 principals in public secondary schools in Enugu State. The application of Cronbach Alpha reliability method yielded co-efficient values of 0.87 and 0.84 for cluster 1 and 2 respectively with an overall reliability coefficient of 0.86. The instrument was administered by the researcher with the help of three research assistants who are teachers in public secondary schools. The instrument was administered to the respondents on the spot and retrieved after completion. In cases where it was impossible to retrieve the instrument immediately, appointment on the date of retrieval was made. This lasted for two weeks. Out of the 400 copies of the instruments administered, 389 copies were retrieved in good condition which amounts to 97.25% questionnaire return rate. The 389 copies were used for the analysis of data. Pearson Product Moment Correlation statistics was used to answer the research questions and test the hypotheses. The decision rule was based on the following guidelines Price et al (2017) provided:

Correlation Coefficient	Interpretations
Plus (+) or minus (-) 0.00 to 0.20	Very Low Relationship
Plus (+) or minus (-) 0.20 to 0.40	Low Relationship
Plus (+) or minus (-) 0.40 to 0.60	Moderate Relationship
Plus (+) or minus (-) 0.60 to 0.80	High Relationship
Plus (+) or minus (-) 0.80 and above	Very High Relationship

While positive coefficient (+) indicate positive relationship between the variables, negative coefficient (-) indicates negative coefficient between the variables. In interpreting the values of the null hypotheses, when p-value is less than or equal to .05 ($p \leq .05$), the null hypothesis will be rejected. On the other hand, when the p-value is greater than .05 ($p > .05$), the null hypothesis will not be rejected, meaning that there is no significant relationship between the variables.

RESULT

Research Question One: *What is the relationship between somatic examination anxiety and academic achievement of public secondary school students in Anambra State?*

Table 1: Summary of Pearson Correlation Analysis on Correlation between Somatic Examination Anxiety and Students Academic Achievement in Public Secondary Schools in Anambra State

		Somatic examination anxiety	Academic achievement	Remark
Somatic examination anxiety	Pearson Correlation	1	-.670**	High Negative Relationship
	Sig, (2-tailed)		.008	
	N	389	389	
Academic achievement	Pearson Correlation	-.670**	1	
	Sig, (2-tailed)	.008		
	N	389	389	

** Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

Data in Table 1 reveals that the Pearson’s Correlation Coefficient is $r = -0.67$. This shows that a high negative relationship exists between somatic examination anxiety and academic achievement of public secondary school students in Anambra State. This implies that somatic examination anxiety would affect academic achievement in public secondary school students in Anambra State. Thus, the Pearson’s Correlation Coefficient r of -0.67 indicate that a high negative relationship exists between somatic examination anxiety and academic achievement of public secondary school students in Anambra State.

Research Question Two: *What is the relationship between cognitive examination anxiety and academic achievement of public secondary school students in Anambra State?*

Table 2: Summary of Pearson Correlation Analysis on Correlation between Cognitive Examination Anxiety and Students Academic Achievement in Public Secondary Schools in Anambra State

		Cognitive examination anxiety	Academic achievement	Remark
Cognitive examination anxiety	Pearson Correlation	1	-.830**	Very High Negative Relationship
	Sig, (2-tailed)		.000	
	N	389	389	
Academic achievement	Pearson Correlation	-.830**	1	
	Sig, (2-tailed)	.000		
	N	389	389	

** Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

Data in Table 2 reveals that the Pearson's Correlation Coefficient is $r = -0.83$. This shows that a very high negative relationship exists between cognitive examination anxiety and academic achievement of public secondary students in Anambra State. This implies that cognitive examination anxiety would affect academic achievement in public secondary school students in Anambra State. Thus, the Pearson's Correlation Coefficient r of -0.83 indicate that a very high negative relationship exists between cognitive examination anxiety and academic achievement of public secondary school students in Anambra State.

Hypothesis One

There is no significant relationship between somatic examination anxiety and academic achievement of public secondary students in Anambra State.

Table 3: Test of Significance of Relationship between Somatic Examination Anxiety and Academic Achievement in Public Secondary Schools in Anambra State

		Correlation		
		Somatic examination anxiety	Academic achievement	Remark
Somatic examination anxiety	Pearson Correlation	1	-0.670^{**}	Significant
	Sig, (2-tailed)		.008	
	N	389	389	
Academic achievement	Pearson Correlation	-0.670^{**}	1	
	Sig, (2-tailed)	.008	389	
	N	389		

** Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

Data presented on Table 3 indicates the correlation coefficient (r) as -0.670 with a p -value = 0.000 . Since the P value of 0.008 is less than $.05$ ($P < .05$), it means that effect of somatic examination anxiety on academic achievement of public secondary school students in Anambra State is statistically significant. This means that there is a significant relationship between somatic examination anxiety and academic achievement of public secondary school students in Anambra State. Thus, the null hypothesis was rejected.

Hypothesis Two

There is no significant relationship between cognitive examination anxiety and academic achievement of public secondary students in Anambra State.

Table 4: Test of Significance of Relationship between Somatic Examination Anxiety and Academic Achievement in Public Secondary Schools in Anambra State

		Correlation		
		Cognitive examination anxiety	Academic achievement	Remark
Cognitive examination anxiety	Pearson Correlation	1	$-.830^{**}$	Significant
	Sig, (2-tailed)		.000	
	N	389	389	
Academic achievement	Pearson Correlation	$-.830^{**}$	1	
	Sig, (2-tailed)	.000	389	
	N	389		

** Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

Data presented on Table 4 indicates the correlation coefficient (r) as -0.830 with a p -value = 0.000 . Since the P value of 0.000 is less than $.05$ ($P < .05$), it means that effect of cognitive examination anxiety on academic achievement of public secondary school students in Anambra State is statistically significant. This means that there is a significant relationship between cognitive examination anxiety and academic achievement of public secondary school students in Anambra State. Thus, the null hypothesis was rejected.

DISCUSSION

The finding of the study revealed that a high negative relationship exists between somatic examination anxiety and academic achievement of public secondary school students in Anambra State. The finding of the study indicate that when students experience somatic examination anxiety it would affect students' academic achievement. This is in agreement with Popovska et al (2024) who reported that higher levels of somatic anxiety were associated with lower academic achievement among undergraduate students. In the same vein, Popovska et al (2024) found that somatic anxiety was a significant predictor of lower test achievement in college students, even after controlling for other factors such as study habits and cognitive test anxiety. Furthermore, finding of the study revealed that a significant relationship between somatic examination anxiety and academic achievement of public secondary school students in Anambra State. This relationship though significant is negative. This is in agreement with Wadi et al. (2022) who revealed that physical manifestations of somatic examination anxiety can have a detrimental effect on cognitive processing and working memory, which are essential for successful achievement on academic tasks. Ilo and Unchukwu (2020) stated that somatic examination anxiety can lead to avoidance behaviors, such as procrastination or incomplete preparation, which can further undermine academic achievement.

The finding of the study revealed that a very high negative relationship exists between cognitive examination anxiety and academic achievement of public secondary school students in Anambra State. The finding of the study indicate that when students experience cognitive examination anxiety it would affect students' academic achievement. This is in consonance with the findings of Wadi et al. (2022) who reported that cognitive anxiety was a significant predictor of lower academic achievement, even after controlling for other factors such as intelligence and prior achievement. Furthermore, Alemu and Feyssa (2020) stated that cognitive examination anxiety can lead to avoidance behaviors, such as procrastination or incomplete preparation, which can further undermine academic achievement. Furthermore, finding of the study revealed that a significant relationship between somatic examination anxiety and academic achievement of public secondary school students in Anambra State. The finding of the study may have resulted because students experiencing cognitive anxiety may also be more likely to engage in negative self-talk or rumination, exacerbating their anxiety and further impairing their achievement. This finding is in agreement with the finding of Onukwufor and Ugwu (2017) who revealed that examination anxiety significantly predicts students' achievement.

CONCLUSION

Based on the finding of the study, the researcher concludes that there is a high negative relationship between examination anxiety and academic achievement of public secondary school students in Anambra State. Furthermore, somatic and cognitive examination anxiety negatively correlates with the academic achievement of public secondary school students in Anambra State. Hence, measures should be put in place to mitigate the negative effects of examination anxiety on public secondary school students' academic achievement.

RECOMMENDATIONS

The following recommendations were made based on the findings of the study:

1. Principals of public secondary schools should implement regular relaxation and mindfulness training sessions for students. This could involve breathing exercises, progressive muscle relaxation, and guided meditation practices, which are known to

reduce physical symptoms of anxiety, such as increased heart rate and muscle tension. By incorporating these exercises into the school routine, students can manage their physical reactions to stress, thus improving their focus and resilience during examinations

2. Teachers and school counsellors should provide workshops on cognitive-behavioural strategies, such as positive self-talk, thought restructuring and anxiety management techniques. These sessions can help students identify and challenge negative thoughts associated with examinations, thereby reducing the mental stress and worry that often hinder academic performance. This approach would promote a more constructive mindset towards examination among secondary school students which will allow them to approach their studies with increased confidence and reduced anxiety.

REFERENCES

- Agnes, O. O., Christopher, A. O., Basil, O. C. E. & Stanley, A. T. (2022). Test anxiety and academic stress as predictors of secondary school students` academic achievement in Physics. *International Journal of Social Sciences and Educational Studies*, 9(4), 172-182.
- Akinola, I. F. & Oredein, A. O. (2021). School climate indices as predictors of students' academic performance in Oyo State, Nigeria. *Teacher Education and Curriculum Studies*, 6(2), 51-60. <https://doi.org/10.11648/j.tecs.20210602.12>.
- Alemu; B.M. & Feyssa, T. (2020). The relationship between test anxiety and academic achievement of grade ten students of Shirka Woveda, Oromia Regional State, Ethiopia. *African Educational Research Journal*, 8(3), 540- 550.
- Amalu, M. N. (2017). Cognitive test anxiety as a predictor of academic achievement among secondary school students in Makurdi Metropolis Benue State. *International Journal of Scientific Research in Education*, 10(4), 362-372.
- Bekomson, A. N., & Mgban T. (2019). Interest in social interaction and selfefficacy among Secondary School Students in Cross River State. *International Journal of of Scientific Research in Education. (IJSRE)*, 2(6), 1-15.
- Dinga J. N., Mwaura A. M. & Ng'ang'a M. W. (2018). Relationship between achievement goal orientation and academic achievement among form three students in Kiambu County, Kenya. *International Journal of Education and Research*, 6(4), 53-68.
- Hamzah, F., Mat, K., Bhagat, V., Amaran,S., & Hassan, H. (2018). Assessing test anxiety among the first year nursing students' of University Sultan Zainal Abidin. *Research Journal of Pharmacy and Technology*, 11(4), 1-11.
- Horsfall, O.D. & Wordu, H. (2023). Influence of test anxiety on academic performance of mathematics students in public senior secondary schools in Port Harcourt Metropolis. *International Journal of Innovative Education Research*, 11(3), 114-128
- Ilo, D. C., & Unachukwu, G. C. (2020). Test anxiety as predictor of senior secondary school students' achievement in english and mathematics in Anambra State. *Socialscientia: Journal of Social Sciences and Humanities*, 5(1), 72–83. Retrieved from <https://journals.aphriapub.com/index.php/SS/article/view/1108>
- Iwuanyanwu, K. U., & Uwadiogwu, C. U. I. (2019). Improvement of teacher quality: A key to Nigeria economic diversification. In W. E. Obiozor., C. O. Madu., B. A. Anukaenyi., U.L. Koledoye., N. C. Mefoh, *Learning and human development in the 21st century*. Kelu Press.
- Mercader-Rubio, I., Ángel, N.G., Silva, S. & Brito-Costa, S. (2023). Levels of somatic anxiety, cognitive anxiety, and self-efficacy in university athletes from a Spanish public university and their relationship with basic psychological needs. *International Journal of Environmental Research in Public Health*, 20, 2415. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph20032415>
- Nwanze, A.C., Konyefa, B.I. and Ezeanya, C.M. (2021). Cognitive style as a determinant of academic achievement of secondary scholl science students in Onitsha Education Zone. *International Journal of Education and Evaluation*, 7(2), 12-24.
- Okobia, D.O. & Oji, J.O. (2020). Test anxiety and academic achievement among undergraduate students in college of education, Agbor, Delta State, Nigeria. *International Journal of Innovative Research & Development*, 10(11), 172-178.

- Oluoch, J. N., Aloka, J. O., and Odongo, B. C. (2018). Test anxiety beliefs as predictor of students' achievement in chemistry in public secondary schools in Kenya. *International Journal of Psychology and Behavioral Sciences*, 8(4), 70-76.
- Onukwufor, J.N. & Ugwu, C. J. (2017). Self-concept, test anxiety and achievement motivation as predictors of academic achievement in physics among secondary school students in Rivers State Nigeria. *Journal of Education and Practice*, 8(33), 99-106.
- Onwugbufo, E. E. & Udebuana, M. C. (2021). Relationship between internet use and academic achievement among public secondary school students in Anambra state. *Journal of Educational Research and Development*, 4(2), 15 – 28.
- Patil, S. G. & Aithala, M. R. (2017). Exam anxiety: Its prevalence and causative factors among Indian medical students. *National Journal of Physiology, Pharmacy and Pharmacology*, 7(12), 1-6.
- Robert, B..J. (2017). *An investigation of attentional bias in test anxiety*.
https://pure.manchester.ac.uk/ws/portalfiles/portal/75067229/FULL_TEXT.PDF.
- Wadi, M., Yusof, M.S.B., Rahim, A.F.B. & Lah (2022). Factors affecting test anxiety: a qualitative analysis of medical students' views. *BMC Psychology*, 10(8), 1-8.
<https://doi.org/10.1186/s40359-021-00715-2>